

Flamelet-Generated-Manifold: Efficient Table Lookup

bwRSE4HPC Project Proposal

Assigned RSEs:	Thomas Isensee ¹ , Marcel Koch ²
Project Partners:	Hagen Müller ³ , Marian Hiestermann ⁴
Scientific field:	Engineering
Subfield:	Computational Fluid Dynamics
Start:	01.04.2026
Duration:	2 months
Type of Work:	Performance Engineering, Refactoring
License:	None
Link:	https://github.com/bwrse4hpc/bwRSE4HPCFoam
Programming Language:	C++
Technologies:	MPI, OpenFoam
Target Cluster:	BwUniCluster3.0

1. Project Summary

The Flamelet-Generated Manifold (FGM) method is an efficient approach to model turbulent combustion in Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations [1]. Instead of solving chemical kinetics during runtime, it relies on pre-computing and tabulating the complete thermochemical state space that can be realized in a given configuration [1,2]. While this significantly reduces computational cost, the resulting lookup tables can become large, particularly when increased modelling detail is required. Additional physical effects typically introduce extra dimensions in the tabulation, which increases the number of stored data points exponentially.

Within the [bwRSE4HPC](#) project [3,4], which provides research software engineering support for high-performance computing (HPC) applications, this work addresses limitations in an existing FGM implementation used in large-scale CFD simulations. The current implementation relies on inefficient data structures and replicates the full table in every process, significantly increasing memory consumption and hindering scalability on HPC systems.

¹Scientific Software Center (SSC), Interdisciplinary Center for Scientific Computing (IWR), Heidelberg University, 69120 Heidelberg, Germany; thomas.isensee@iwr.uni-heidelberg.de

²Scientific Computing Center (SCC), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), 76021 Karlsruhe, Germany; marcel.koch@kit.edu

³Institute of Applied Thermo and Fluid Dynamics, Technical University of Applied Sciences Mannheim, 68163 Mannheim, Deutschland; hagen.mueller@th-mannheim.de

⁴MTU Aero Engines AG, Munich 80995, Germany; marian.hiestermann@mtu.de

2. Problem Statement

The FGM method reduces cost at runtime, but practical high-dimensional tables, often with five or more dimensions, create a major RAM bottleneck in parallel CFD.

In the current implementation, each process replicates all tabulated quantities, so total memory demand increases with core count and limits feasible table resolution on cluster nodes. Although lookup runtime is largely independent of table size, memory scaling and non-ideal parallel efficiency constrain large-scale use. The core problem is to reduce table memory footprint and replication overhead without sacrificing interpolation accuracy or lookup performance.

3. Suggested Solution

The proposed redesign focuses on reducing memory overhead and removing the current hard-coding to four table dimensions, while remaining compatible with OpenFOAM and the C++14 standard used in this code base. The first step is to replace the deeply nested `List<List<List<scalarList>>> defaultList;` storage of tabulated data with a single contiguous array combined with explicit dimension metadata. Extents and strides can be stored in fixed-size stack-allocated containers such as `std::array`, which avoids further heap fragmentation and improves cache locality during table lookup.

To reduce memory consumption further, the redesigned implementation should support both double-precision and single-precision storage of tabulated data. This makes it possible to select the precision level according to the accuracy requirements of a given application while potentially reducing the table memory footprint substantially in cases where single precision is sufficient.

As an optional abstraction layer for such contiguous storage, it may also be useful to evaluate container types such as `Kokkos::View`. While this project targets CPU execution only, `Kokkos::View` provides a well-defined multidimensional array abstraction with explicit memory layout and indexing semantics. In particular, it supports both compile-time and runtime dimensions and can also wrap externally allocated memory through unmanaged views. This could make it a convenient wrapper around a flat table representation. However, introducing such a dependency would need to be evaluated carefully with respect to complexity and integration with the existing OpenFOAM code base.

Since the current implementation stores each queried property in a separate table, the redesign will assess the potential of a unified array-of-structures-style layout in which all tabulated properties associated with one support point are stored contiguously, provided they share the same tabulation grid. Such a layout might better reflect the typical usage pattern where several thermochemical quantities are interpolated simultaneously from the same coordinates and interpolation weights, and may improve cache utilization. However, this approach implicitly requires a common grid resolution for all variables, which may not be optimal if different quantities exhibit varying degrees of smoothness. Therefore, the benefits of improved memory locality must be balanced against the loss of flexibility in choosing variable-specific resolutions.

On top of this storage redesign, the interpolation implementation should be generalized so that the same code path supports an arbitrary number of tabulation axes. This removes the need to introduce separate classes such as `D5LinearInterpolation` or `D6LinearInterpolation` whenever additional physical effects require higher-dimensional tables. A dimension-generic implementation also improves maintainability, since future extensions would no longer require duplicating interpolation logic for each supported dimensionality.

The redesign should also preserve flexibility with respect to the tabulation itself. In particular, it may be useful to assess support for both uniform and non-uniform tabulation grids, so that the resolution can be adapted to the behavior of the underlying quantities. Non-uniform sampling may reduce storage requirements by placing support points more densely in regions with strong gradients and more sparsely in smoother regions. Likewise, higher-order interpolation could be explored as a possible way to achieve acceptable accuracy on coarser grids. However, both options introduce important trade-offs. Non-uniform grids generally require more complex interval lookup, for example through binary searches. Higher-order interpolation substantially increases stencil size in higher dimensions; for example, cubic interpolation in six dimensions would already require $4^6 = 4096$ support values per query. In addition, higher-order schemes may introduce oscillations, overshoots, or otherwise non-physical interpolated values. These aspects therefore have to be evaluated carefully against the expected gains in storage efficiency and must not compromise lookup performance or numerical robustness. The implementation should remain flexible enough that uniform grids with linear interpolation continue to be available as a robust baseline, while more advanced options can be tested where beneficial.

The redesign should further address the dominant memory bottleneck on HPC systems by avoiding one full table copy per MPI rank whenever possible. Instead, the preferred target is one shared table per node, so that processes on the same node can reuse the same table data rather than replicating it in every address space. One possible mechanism for achieving this is the use of memory-mapped files (`mmap`), as reported in Ref. [5]. In this approach, the table could be stored in a contiguous file-backed representation and mapped into the address space of multiple MPI processes on the same node. Because the operating system page cache allows physical memory pages to be shared between processes, this may avoid explicit in-memory replication while preserving a simple array-based lookup interface. However, its practical suitability depends on factors such as access locality, page-cache behavior, file-system performance, portability, and integration with the target HPC environment.

4. Milestones

- **Phase 1:** Analyze the current table-loading and interpolation path, define the generic table layout, and specify how contiguous storage, dimension metadata, and OpenFOAM integration should interact.
- **Phase 2:** Implement the new contiguous storage format and dimension-generic linear interpolation while preserving the existing lookup workflow as the functional baseline.
- **Phase 3:** Extend the redesign with node-local shared table storage for MPI processes where supported, explore file-backed sharing mechanisms such as `mmap` as a possible alternative

implementation path, and add optional single-precision table storage as a configurable memory-saving mode.

- **Phase 4:** Validate the new implementation against the current version by comparing memory usage, lookup performance, and numerical agreement

5. Deliverables

- A refactored table lookup implementation based on contiguous storage
- A dimension-generic linear interpolation implementation that supports arbitrary table dimensionality without separate per-dimension interpolation classes.
- Support for node-local shared table storage across MPI ranks where the target HPC environment permits it.
- Optional single-precision table storage as a selectable memory-optimization path.
- Updated benchmark-ready code for comparing the redesigned implementation against the current lookup approach.

6. Expected Contributions

- Access to *bwRSE4HPCFoam*, i.e., the source code repository specifically set up for this collaboration
- Access to the cluster-specific compute-time allocation (German: Rechenvorhaben) if applicable
- Availability for regular online meetings
- Appropriate acknowledgment and co-authorship in scientific publications directly resulting from the added capabilities.

Bibliography

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